

**A first dialectometric approach
to contact-induced vs language-internal variation
in inner Asia Minor Greek**

Abstract

This paper reports on the application of dialectometric techniques to measure the degrees of association between contact-induced and language-internal variation in inner Asia Minor Greek varieties (i.e., those of Cappadocian, Phrasiot, and Silliot). Our methods include correlative analyses (between pairs of the datasets and between them and two aspects of geography) as well as multidimensional scaling and cluster analysis (for each dataset), which allow us, on the one hand, to draw conclusions about the associations between contact-induced and language-internal phenomena as well as the distributions of dialects, and, on the other hand, to directly compare our results to those coming from traditional dialectology. The various analyses show that the two discerning factors are crucial in many ways as they define different landscapes. Interestingly, dialectometric results confirm non-dialectometric classifications only partially.

1. Introduction

Although dialectometric approaches have contributed significantly to the advancement of dialectology, by applying computational and statistical analyses for the discovery of more abstract patterns which would otherwise remain hidden (Wieling & Nerbonne 2015 for the recent advances in dialectometry), Modern Greek dialects have been largely absent from this field of research. The existing literature was mainly related to the traditional isoglossic methods (Trudgill 2003 and references therein), which have been the subject of heavy criticism (e.g. Bloomfield 1933, 341; Nerbonne 2009, 179, 190–191). Luckily, digital Greek dialectal data that have been made available in the last decade have proved a fruitful empirical ground for the application of innovative computational approaches to Modern Greek dialects.

Therefore, this article aims to present and discuss the first dialectometric analyses of inner Asia Minor Greek dialects (i.e., Cappadocian, Phrasiot, and Silliot), with the aim of addressing the question of to what degree contact-induced (henceforth CI) vs language-internal (henceforth LI) phenomena define different dialectal landscapes. To do so, we estimate the linguistic distances among 19 varieties (given data availability) spoken in inner Asia Minor based on 279 linguistic phenomena. The original set of phenomena is classed under two heads: (a) CI and (b) LI phenomena, which are treated both separately – different data matrices (subsets of the original dataset) based on specific qualitative criteria – and cumulatively, so that hidden patterns are revealed and identified by using several dialectometric analyses (Spruit, Heeringa & Nerbonne 2009; Scherrer & Stoeckle 2016 for similar approaches). Special emphasis is also placed on testing the sufficiency of the existing isogloss-dependent dialect areas in the studied dialectal landscape.

This work was financially supported by the “[Andreas Mentzelopoulos Scholarships](#)”. Dialectal resources were provided by the DiCaDLand project (“[Digitizing the Cappadocian Dialectal Landscape](#)”) funded by the GSRT and the HFRI. The authors are grateful to Angela Ralli, Petros Karatsareas and Metin Bağrıaçık for providing access to their dialectal databases.

The article is structured as follows: Section 2 formulates the dialectal landscape of the varieties addressed in this work. Section 3 describes the datasets and the adopted methodology. In Section 4, the exact degrees of association between CI and LI phenomena and the degrees of correlation with geography and dialect areas are discussed. Moreover, we plot our results using multidimensional scaling and fuzzy clustering to provide a (geo)graphical visualization of the degrees of observed associations and compare non-dialectometric and dialectometric classifications. Our analyses suggest that the two discerning factors are important as they illustrate different aspects of the existing variation in many ways. Interestingly, our dialectometric results verify the non-dialectometric (isogloss-dependent) classifications only partially. The paper ends with conclusions (Section 5) and a list of references.

2. The inner Asia Minor Greek dialectal landscape

The inner Asia Minor Greek (henceforth iAMGr; Kontosopoulos 2008 [1981], 6 ff.) dialect group comprises of three related dialects that were originally spoken by Orthodox Christian communities in the Cappadocian plateau; Cappadocian, Pharasiot, and Silliot. The relevant position of these dialects can be seen in Map 1.

The sociocultural settings under which the Greek-speaking communities of inner Asia Minor evolved from the 11th century onwards significantly affected the shaping of iAMGr, which developed for centuries in intense language contact with Turkish, on the one hand, and in relative isolation from the rest of the Greek-speaking areas of the west, on the other (Dawkins 1916; Karatsareas 2011; 2013; Manolessou 2019 for details). In this vein, iAMGr has often been referred to as “an excellent example of heavy structural borrowing” (Thomason & Kaufman 1988, 215). Particularly, drawing on Dawkins (1916), Thomason & Kaufman (1988, 93–94) enumerate a variety of lexical and grammatical innovations found in the three dialects that make such a strong case for language contact in iAMGr so as to claim that, while most of the varieties “clearly retain enough inherited Greek material to count as Greek dialects in the full genetic sense” – the ‘Greek substratum’ in terms of Dawkins (1916, 212) – “a few dialects may be close to or even over the border of nongenetic development”. In the same line, some scholars argue that Cappadocian, Pharasiot, and, to a lesser extent, Silliot belong to a typological group distinct from all other Modern Greek dialects and, crucially, to one that shares many features with Turkish, justifying its separate treatment and study from the rest of the Greek dialects (Karatsareas 2011, 35–38; 2013, 198–202 for an overview).

The most widely accepted classification of iAMGr varieties dates back to Dawkins (1916), who divided the iAMGr into two branches: a core branch that includes Cappadocian and Pharasiot, and a more peripheral branch with Silliot as its sole member (Dawkins 1916, 206). Following Dawkins (1916, 204), “the dialect of Pharsa is least affected by Turkish and that of Cappadocia most; Silli holding an intermediate position”. Moreover, Dawkins (1916, 208–209) assumed that the Cappadocian dialect is further classified into five groups based on isoglosses that reflect the depth and extent of Turkish influence. This partition corresponds to the geographically defined grouping recently revised by Janse (2008, 191; forthcoming). Turkish was thought to have a stronger influence in the southern Cappadocian zone, while villages of the northern zone were thought to be less influenced by Turkish. The isogloss-borne partitioning of the iAMGr dialect landscape and the continuum of influence of Turkish are shown in Map 1.

Taking all these conditions together, iAMGr constitutes an intriguing linguistic ground upon which computational-inspired methodologies may be very fruitful, contributing to the development of variationist studies and linguistic theory.

3. Data and methods

The standard dialectometric pipeline involves several steps (e.g. Goebel 2011, 439), in order to obtain a reliable generic depiction of dialectal landscapes. In the following, we present the methodological steps adopted in the present study (also summarized in Figure 2).

Map 1: Dialect zones and degrees of Turkish influence (based on Dawkins 1916, 209; Janse 2008, 191; forthcoming; Karatsareas 2011, 38)

3.1 Linguistic matrices

Data is drawn from the Interactive Dialectal Atlas of the Cappadocian Dialects (<http://cappadocian.upatras.gr/en/atlas>; Melissaropoulou, Bompolas & Tsimpouris 2022 for details). The atlas contains 429 variables (11,375 variants) for 20 inquiry points (based on data availability). Atlas' data have been modified to meet the specific requirements of our study. Specifically,

(a) we have unified variables (and their variants) that have been distinct in the case of atlas for organizational and technical reasons (such as in the case of the complementizers);

(b) we allowed variants to occur as sets in order to account for multiple dominant variants attested in the atlas;

(c) given the categorical nature of data, we have excluded the systematic phonological changes in the levels of morphology and syntax, by keeping only the phonological instances of the variables;

(d) we excluded some maps which are not categorical in nature but rather fall under the category of string data (e.g. numerals);

(e) we omitted a specific inquiry point (that is of Semendere) due to many nulls.

Linguistic data are aggregated into a data matrix which contains a row for each inquiry point and a column for each working map or linguistic item. The cells of the matrix represent the variants that are used in each inquiry point for a given phenomenon.

Figure 1: Two-stage annotation of the original data matrix

Afterwards, we proceeded to a two-stage annotation (Figure 1) of the original data matrix, using a series of dummy variables that served our analysis. First, linguistic variables were classified into two categories: (a) CI phenomena and (b) LI phenomena, based on the existing relevant literature. In those cases, where there is no consensus in the existing studies on the (non) contact-induced nature of the phenomena, we deliberately followed the line of thought of the DiCaDLanD project, as cited in the “Notes for further reading” section (Melissaropoulou, Bompolas & Tsimpouris 2022, 142–143). In the case of CI phenomena, we further annotated their associated variants to distinguish the different instances that are related to contact – for example, to distinguish word-based formations (an extreme incorporation of Turkish grammatical features into the Greek grammatical system) from stem-based formations. All the different Greek variants have been given the same dummy variable as we wanted to distinguish the qualities based only on the extent of Turkish influence. The outcome is three data matrices:

	Places	Variables	Variants
CI phenomena	19	162	3,541
LI phenomena	19	117	2,898
Complete dataset	19	279	6,698

Table 1: Number of places, linguistic variables, and variants in the data matrices

3.2 Linguistic distance matrices

To measure the correlations between the three linguistic matrices, we should first measure the dialect distances within them. Thus, the three linguistic data matrices were uploaded onto Gabmap (Nerbonne et al. 2011; Leinonen, Çöltekin & Nerbonne 2016) to obtain the aggregate (19×19) distance matrices of each linguistic matrix for further

analyses and various visualizations. Given the categorical nature of our data, it has been processed using binary comparison.

3.3 Geographic distance matrices

One aspect of the present paper focuses on the degree to which linguistic distances are explained by geography, including not only plain distance but also areal partition, representing the traditional assumptions depicted in Map 1. In this line, two more (19×19) distance matrices are used, capturing different aspects of geography:

- (a) a matrix with distances in kilometers between every pair of locations; and
- (b) a value distance matrix in which sites are partitioned into the a priori-defined dialect areas by using a series of dummy binary (0, 1) variables (Nerbonne 2013).

4. Data analysis

4.1 Correlative analysis

The purpose of correlative analysis is to assess the degree of association between two distance matrices by comparing them, using the Mantel test. The matrices may either be linguistic distance matrices (e.g. comparing CI to LI phenomena) or geographic distance matrices (e.g. comparing LI phenomena to plain distance/dialect zones).

4.1.1 Correlation between linguistic and geographic distance matrices

One may wonder whether the existing variation is rather a consequence of sites engaging in a partition of relatively homogeneous dialect areas than of continuous variation along the dimension of distance between sites. Interestingly, we showed that the proposed dialect areas of iAMGr, although based on *linguistic* features, capture the *social* conditions of these communities as regards the Turkish influence. The quantitative approach allows us to investigate whether these dialect areas (and the following social parameters) contribute to linguistic distance, using the value matrix in which sites are partitioned into areas as independent variable (see Section 3.3). Following Nerbonne (2013, 232), if dialect areas are true, then the areal factor should turn out to be significant, and plain distance will not be an explanatory factor. Similarly, areal differences should explain nothing if the continuum approach is sufficient.

Table 2 shows that the two discerning concepts of geography explain the variance of each dataset in different pathways. Firstly, concerning the CI phenomena, geographic distance can explain only 21% of the existing variance, meaning that there is much variance explained by other factors. Hence, it is no coincidence that the social dimension reflected by the dialect areas explains the observed variance almost twice as much (40%). On the other hand, the results are reversed in the case of the LI phenomena; phenomena of Greek origin are poorly explained areally (32%), compared to the percentage of the explained variance by plain distance (49%). We propose that this is the outcome of the relative weight traditional dialectology gives upon CI phenomena to classify the studied varieties, neglecting the role of LI phenomena. As a result, dialect areas cannot adequately capture the areal variation of the phenomena of Greek origin.

Moreover, the high score of geographic distance supports Dawkins' (1916, 211) assumption that this type of phenomena is not so restricted in its range, having a fairly uniform distribution over the whole area.

Figure 2: The methodological flowchart

Finally, when we look at the entire dataset, we see more balanced results; both dialect areas and geographic distances explain nearly equally the entire dataset; 42% and 41%, respectively.

	Areal correlation (r)	Explained variance areally (r²×100)	Geographic distance correlation (r)	Explained variance by distance (r²×100)
Complete dataset	0.65	42%	0.64	41%
LI phenomena	0.57	32%	0.70	49%
CI phenomena	0.63	40%	0.46	21%

Table 2: Correlations between linguistic and areal/geographic distances

4.1.2 Correlation between linguistic distance matrices

Turning now to the comparison between different linguistic distance matrices, we computed the correlations between the different subsets as well as between each subset and the complete dataset. The results are summarized in Table 3.

	Correlation (r)	Explained variance (r²×100)
Complete dataset ~ LI phenomena	0.95	90%
Complete dataset ~ CI phenomena	0.94	88%
CI phenomena ~ LI phenomena	0.80	64%

Table 3: Correlations between linguistic distance matrices

It is not unexpected that correlations between each subset and the whole dataset are extremely significant and typically have high coefficients on the grounds that both LI and CI phenomena are subsets of the complete dataset and therefore not independent. However, the correlations between CI and LI phenomena show smaller coefficients in comparison to the correlations outlined before, which is to be expected given that their distance matrices can be thought of as independent of one another. The poorer score of the association between them (64%) means that they exhibit different patterns of variation, to some extent at least, and should be taken both into account in order to present the existing variation more accurately.

4.2 Visualizations

Correlation analyses revealed that: (a) a good deal of variation is not explained by the suggested isogloss-dependent areal differences (especially in the case of LI phenomena), and (b) the different linguistic matrices should vary as regards the linguistic landscapes they define. To visualize these associations and illustrate both the continuous nature of the data and the dialect groupings, we use two dialectometric techniques provided by Gabmap. Namely, we employ *multi-dimensional scaling* (MDS) and *fuzzy clustering* (Nerbonne et al. 2011, 76, 81–83; Leinonen, Çöltekin & Nerbonne 2016, 75–76, 79 and references therein for details).

4.2.1 Multi-dimensional scaling

In Figure 3, we display our results plotting the sites of all studied varieties in a two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system to describe the continuous transitions from one dialect area into the other.

Figure 3: MDS plots

Our results suggest once again that the two discerning parameters are crucial for revealing and accounting for the various patterns of variation. On the one hand, CI phenomena result in an arrangement ranging from $-$ Turkish to $+$ Turkish, reflecting the social conditions and the degrees of bilingualism of the communities, addressed in Section 2. On the other hand, LI phenomena reveal a reverse effect, compared to the contact parameter; the distances among Cappadocian and Pharasiot subdialects are eliminated, while the distances among the three main dialectal clusters escalate. We assume that these features mark the Greek substratum not only of Cappadocian, as Dawkins (1916, 211–212) assumes, but of each dialectal group, exhibiting enough uniformity to justify their treatment as separate dialects. Finally, when all phenomena are considered cumulatively, both dialectal and subdialectal clusters (and continua) emerge, aligning only partially with the general assumptions of the relevant dialectological research (for which see Section 4.2.2). Remarkably, dialectometric results based on the contact

parameter (top-left plot) are comparable to the non-dialectometric continuum of Turkish influence presented in Map 1.

Interestingly, the variety of Sinasos is the most deviant Cappadocian variety, based on the complete dataset and CI phenomena. This is anticipated given the fact that it is more conservative and vastly infected by the common Greek because of the Greek school and its close relationship to Constantinople (Dawkins 1916, 18, 27–28). Thus, it does not participate in the novelties presented in the rest of the Cappadocian varieties, many of which are attributed to the contact with Turkish. This also explains its closeness to Phrasiot, which is influenced by Turkish the least, in the MDS plots.

4.2.2 Fuzzy clustering

The MDS plots in Figure 3 show that, despite the continuous nature of the dialects, varieties also seem to cluster together, forming dialect groups. However, MDS does not provide us with a more detailed image of this partition. Clustering is very useful in dialectometry since its results divide sites into groups, making it easier to compare our quantitative work to older findings. Thus, we plot the results using *fuzzy clustering*, a reliable dialectometric technique developed to constrain the known instability of the clustering methods (Nerbonne 2011, 485–487).

Clustering results demonstrate that the two types of phenomena yield different patterns of areal variation and should be examined separately before being aggregated. On the one hand, CI phenomena present a fine-grained (sub)grouping, reflecting the depth of Turkish influence. Remarkably, this type of phenomena gives the varieties such an inhomogeneity that the members of Cappadocian are not clustered as a single dialect. More specifically, Sinasos is clustered with Phrasiot varieties, reflecting their relatedness as regards the absence of Turkisms (see also the top-right plot in Figure 3). On the other hand, the top-right plot presents a reverse effect; LI phenomena give enough uniformity to the three main dialects so as to be treated as separate groups with 100% probability. However, focusing on Cappadocian varieties, LI phenomena are not restricted in range, having a more wide and uniform distribution, meaning that we cannot obtain good correlations at the local level (within dialects) but at a larger scale (over dialects). This is evidenced by the low percentages of the resultant clusters, meaning that the varieties cannot be put into one subgroup with high probability. Finally, when all variables are considered, it is surprising that the Cappadocian varieties do not emerge as a single dialect. This must be impeded by the special status of the variety of Sinasos, which is only a peripheral member of North Cappadocian with a relative low percentage (61%). Although the variety of Sinasos shares a common Greek substratum with Cappadocian (top-right dendrogram, see also the top-right plot in Figure 3), it is closer to Phrasiot than Cappadocian with respect to the absence of Turkisms (see also the top-left plot in Figure 3), making it the most deviant Cappadocian variety. So, when we take Sinasos out of the clustering, the rest of the Cappadocian dialects are 100% likely to come out as a single dialect.

Finally, comparing our results to those coming from traditional dialectology, the subdivisions proposed by Dawkins (1916, 209–211, Map 1) are supported by our results to some extent only. Specifically, Dawkins' five-split subdivision of Cappadocian varieties based on CI phenomena (1916, 209) is supported by our results to some extent, especially for North Cappadocian (with the exception of Sinasos). As for the southern group, instead of Aravan and Ghurzono, Fertek is clustered with Ulaghatsh. Moreover, Axo and Misti do not constitute either a transitional zone between the two major groups or even a separate subgroup with respect to the Turkisms.

Figure 4: Clustering with noise (=0.2), limit (=60%), using group + weighted average method. Top-Left: CI phenomena. Top-Right: LI phenomena. Bottom-Left: Complete dataset (including Sinasos). Bottom-Right: Complete dataset (excluding Sinasos)

Additionally, the general north–south division of Cappadocian dialects proposed by Dawkins (1916, 210–211) based on LI phenomena is really questioned by our results. In particular, geographically northern varieties of Potamia and Delmeso are clustered with southern varieties, together with Axo and Misti, which once again do not constitute a ‘border zone’ between the two groups. Even when we turn to the complete dataset, Axo and Misti are clustered with southwest Cappadocian (i.e., Aravan and Ghurzono). Remarkably, the variety of Ulaghatsh is a peripheral member of Cappadocian when LI phenomena are tested.

5. Conclusions

To sum up, we performed several dialectometric analyses directed towards the CI and LI phenomena of iAMGr. The characteristics of these layouts were quantified so that patterns in them can be identified. These patterns led to a better understanding of the factors that are responsible for the ways in which linguistic features develop in space and crucially to more precise conclusions about the iAMGr dialectological landscape. Specifically:

(a) Correlations to geography show that CI phenomena are explained better by dialect areas than by geographic distance. The reverse effect is observed for LI phenomena. We interpret this result based on the social situations reflected by the proposed classifications, focusing on the extent of Turkish influence. Moreover, we propose that this is the outcome of the relative weight traditional dialectology gives upon CI phenomena to classify the studied varieties, neglecting the role of LI phenomena. As a result, dialect areas cannot adequately capture the areal variation of the phenomena of Greek origin. On the other hand, geographic distance can explain better the wider arrangement of LI phenomena within each of the three dialects, giving enough uniformity to their varieties so as to justify their treatment as separate dialects. Finally, correlations between the two types of phenomena show poor scores, suggesting the two datasets exhibit different patterns of variance.

(b) Different patterns of variance emerged when we tested out the data using MDS. The two-dimensional plots depicted different aspects of the data. CI phenomena resulted in an arrangement, ranging from –Turkish to +Turkish, which is equivalent to the non-dialectometric assumptions and depicts the social situations of the varieties under investigation. Conversely, phenomena of Greek origin, marking the common substratum of the dialects, lead to a clear-cut partition separating the three dialects, which is in line with the results coming from the correlational analysis.

(c) The above-mentioned results were also evident when we used clustering. Each parameter yields different results which are only partially aligned to the dominant traditional assumptions. In addition, fuzzy clustering shed light on the special status of Sinasos, which is closer to Pharasiot as for the absence of Turkisms and closer to Cappadocian as for its Greek substratum, attributing enough uncertainty to clustering the Cappadocian varieties together.

Overall, our results suggest that, before aggregating, linguistic features should be examined and compared separately, so that discerning factors that determine the various patterns can be identified (Pickl & Rumpf 2012). We aspire that such a dialectometric approach to iAMGR is advantageous in that the areal distribution of language varieties is not pre-structured by linguistic assumptions underlying the selection of isoglosses but is generated from a huge set of data.

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Keywords: dialectometry, correlative dialectometry, multi-dimensional scaling, fuzzy clustering, inner Asia Minor Greek, Cappadocian, Pharasiot, Silliot, contact-induced variation, language-internal variation